

Neurospicy Libraries

Report 2: Workload Management

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Introduction

This report details the findings of the second survey conducted as part of the Neurospicy Libraries project. This project has involved several activities, one of which is surveying people within a peer support network of neurodivergent library employees across three different areas of difficulty in the workplace.

This second survey and report focusses on workload in terms of amount of work, but also the type and structure, and on productivity, organisation and what is generally termed 'executive function' as it related to assigned work. This was identified as the second most important area of concern in an initial survey which asked about different potential areas of focus.

The focus of these reports is not to go through a full objective research process with shared data, comprehensive literature reviews and systematic analysis. The approach is much more informal, and can be thought of as a collection of anonymous lived experiences that are communicated through the Neurospicy Project leads who are acting as 'cover' for the respondents who engaged. Participants would not necessarily disclose their neurodivergency publicly or even within a closed workplace, and even further than this would not submit responses of this nature to a formal research project even if anonymity was offered and prefer to offer information to grass roots, practicality focussed projects lead by peers only. Responses do however act as evidence to support communication from the Neurospicy Libraries project leads – this is not just us, this is the voice of many individuals working in libraries now who are struggling in private.

There were 26 respondents to this survey

Respondents are all self identified neurodivergent individuals working in libraries in the UK, and while the project is affiliated with academic libraries north, they do include individuals working in other areas of the UK and other library sectors outside of academic settings.

Participants were asked to respond to a range of free text questions via Google Forms, and were not asked about any contextual information beyond how they would describe their neurodivergency. All responses were anonymous. Participants were not asked about data sharing beforehand and so the full responses are not available to be shared.

Literature Review and Analysis

No formal literature review or analysis methodology has been formulated. Responses were read through in full and the most common themes collated in a subjective manner, with example responses that convey the essence of that theme offered. They are then linked to the most salient advice available across a range of resources and guides in a similarly informal manner.

Results

Q1: What problems, difficulties or issues do you encounter with regards to workload, particularly focussing on the amount of work you encounter?

Theme 1: Multi-tasking and Interrupting Urgent Tasks

"...distractions from new work coming in when trying to focus on a task..."

"Expectations of immediate replies, when trying to focus on project work."

"Manning the desk whilst being in a teams meeting."

Theme 2: Unclear Instructions and Deadlines

"Ambiguous deadlines."

"...doing the work without explicit directions..."

"...knowing what was expected of me if it isn't communicated clearly leads to anxiety and overwhelm..."

Theme 3: Variable Workloads

"Workload unpredictable at times due to the nature of my role and needing to be responsive to academic staff and students at short notice as well..."

"Sometimes there is not enough work to keep me busy while I'm at work, or sometimes there is work to do but I'm too exhausted or burnt out to do it."

"My issue is that I either have feast or famine with the amount of work that I encounter."

Theme 4: Over-promising

"I struggle not to over commit and I've learned to turn my hyper focus into hyper productivity, but that can of course lead to burn out if I don't manage it."

"I have a tendency to say yes to everything, regardless of whether I have time to do it!"

"I feel like I can't say no to extra work because saying yes is a one word answer, but to avoid looking rude or selfish, an answer of no has to be much more complicated with multiple reasons."

Theme 5: Prioritisation Skills and Task Transition Time

"Knowing how to prioritise."

"...find it hard to move on or transition into another task until that one is done (even though it isn't a priority)..."

"...focus/task switching can be a problem..."

"I end up multitasking and prioritizing the wrong thing when other things are much more urgent."

Q2: What do you do personally to overcome these problems, difficulties or issues with workload?

Theme 1: Extreme Planning and Organisation

"Master and weekly to do lists including numerical and other coding to emphasis priority/order of tasks."

"I try using different systems to keep track of projects, action items, to do lists."

"Plan everything as far in advance as possible, to give plenty of time for error checking."

Theme 2: Extra Effort and Extra Hours

"Usually end up putting in extra time to catch up with everything."

"I script conversations out."

"On the days I feel very motivated/hyper focused I get several days of work done."

Theme 3: Autonomy and Control

"...the autonomy to do things how I want to."

"Make sure everything has a deadline."

"...anticipate difficult tasks and do them before I am asked."

Theme 4: Physical Accommodations

"Keep a weighted lap blanket in the office, and multiple kinds of headphones, and a yoga mat."

"Noise cancelling headphones."

"Coloured overlays."

Theme 5: Social Accommodations

"...ask others not to send long emails - or highlight the relevant bit."

"I have made it clear to my colleagues that I need very clear instructions."

"I ask my colleagues and direct reports to contact me via Instant Messenger rather than email as my inbox is overwhelming."

Q3: What mitigations does your workplace put in place to help with any problems, difficulties or issues with workload?

Theme 1: Nothing

"I have not declared my ADHD diagnosis to them."

"None, I am not sure what I could ask for."

"I haven't disclosed it, already a minority."

Theme 2: Issues with Understaffing (negative)

"I am in desperate need of an assistant manager but have been told this isn't a priority."

"I am essentially doing the work of two jobs now... We are almost criminally understaffed."

"...the issues I face are a product of the institutional structure but the issues I have because of ADHD exacerbate what is an already challenging workload."

Theme 3: Allowing Autonomy and Control

"I have a supportive manager who will always check with me in terms of capacity before she/other team members ask for my involvement in tasks and commitments."

"...whenever I say I do not have capacity or that something isn't a priority for me, this is always respected."

"...my role is very self starting and autonomous with minimal management oversight."

Theme 4: Following Through on Social Accommodations

"...not asking me to do things they know I'd be into because they know there is too much..."

"The ability/permission to walk out of a meeting if I'm triggered."

"Regularly check in with everyone..."

Theme 5: Environmental Accommodations

"...a more quiet office environment..."

"My own office, with a door that I keep closed and locked most of the time."

"Lighting that I control."

Q4: What problems, difficulties or issues do you encounter with regards to work, particularly focussing on the type and structure of work you encounter?

Theme 1: All the Issues Highlighted in Q1

"I get very easily distracted by noise and other people's conversation."

"...constant interruptions."

"Unclear expectations."

Theme 2: Task Transition Effort

"It is hard for me to motivate myself when I need to self-motivate."

"...starting tasks that I find uninteresting but are a necessary part of my job is a particular challenge as I often struggle to find the motivation to do this..."

"I also struggle with task changing. It can be difficult for me to go from helping the students then back at my desk. It can take awhile before I can adjust to the new task."

Theme 3: Structure, Routine and Predictability

"I have explored having a pattern of working from home and being on campus and having that be the same every week, and also having meetings in the morning only and afternoons as desk work, but it doesn't work for the job I have."

"...one issue is when having to work in teams and contribute ideas without preparation, e.g., especially when team meeting is called for quick solutions/discussion which I often can't contribute to as I need time to think about things..."

"My line manager has an impulsive style of working which is at odds with my preference for highly structured, organised work."

Theme 4: Managing Emotions and Reactions

"I can have strong emotional reactions to things I determine to be unfair or unjust."

"I have masked and kept things hidden because if I declare my conditions then my employer might over-react and view me as something 'to be managed' or incompetent."

"Surprises can be difficult for me to process, so those random emails from boss where they need info quickly can be really challenging..."

Theme 5: Social Understanding

"...socially I miss cues and people probably mistrust me for it."

"Not able to have transparent conversations because of professional office culture."

"...anxiously go with whatever seems to make the most sense and hope it turns out to be the right guess..."

Q5: What do you do personally to overcome these problems, difficulties or issues with work type and structure?

Theme 1: All the Issues Highlighted in Q2

"Lots of lists, working out details."

"...brown noise playing to drown out external stimuli."

"...headphones..."

Theme 2: Saying No

"I don't accept full days of meetings, I suggest different times."

"I've got better at pushing back on requests from my line manager when they drop something on me at short notice."

"...I try to outsource some accountability to coworkers and my boss and dept head, who are really kind about it."

Theme 3: Focus Time and Turning Off Notifications

"Structure time to do one job at a time."

"Have my Teams set to voicemail so I don't get interrupted by random calls and also close other programmes with pop ups e.g. outlook when doing certain tasks."

"If I've got a lot of small meetings or I'll definitely be interrupted a lot in another way, I just won't do a deep background tasks alongside that, I'll block off my calendar and wait to do it then."

Theme 4: Masking and Emotional Regulation

"My team know that I will often go for 'an angry walk' - a 10 minute walk around the campus so that I can calm down when something irritates me and find that this is a good way for me to reflect before I react."

"Masking, hiding my true feelings."

"I try to slow down, but that doesn't always work."

Theme 5: Accountability and 'Buddies'

"...have previously had an adhd accountability partner (not a work colleague...)"

"Make myself accountable to someone else."

"I try to ask as many clarifying questions as I can get away with, sometimes asking colleagues beforehand what format they'd prefer me to send questions in."

Q6: What mitigations does your workplace put in place to help with any problems, difficulties or issues with work type and structure?

Theme 1: Nothing

“None that I know of.”

“None, I am not sure what I could ask for.”

“I haven't requested mitigations.”

Theme 2: Extra Guidance, or Lack of it

“My workplace is not that good at having official procedures and documents.”

“Extra guidance/structure.”

“I had a Manager that made great flow charts and built in structure to help us know what to do and when.”

Theme 3: Flexibility

“I have a lot of flexibility to manage my own calendar so I get to work from home on occasion.”

“There is a strong culture of trust rather than micromanaging or tracking hours to the minute... I am never limited to just working in one place.”

“My manager does try to give a variety in the type of tasks given.”

Theme 4: Advance Warning

“Given warning/sent emails in advance as far as possible.”

“...they'll email or schedule a meeting rather than surprising me with a knock on the door or a phone call.”

Theme 5: Allowing Processing Time

“Most of my colleagues know not to expect a quick response from me.”

“They accept that I'm going to do the above and support it.”

Q7: What problems, difficulties or issues do you encounter with regards to productivity, organisation and executive function around getting work done?

Theme 1: Attention Deficit

"Can i just say "adhd"... I have a lot of trouble with executive function especially when I am not medicated."

"I find it hard to concentrate or get brain fog/mind block sensation if I can't fidget, move around."

"...going off on tangents, staring into space sometimes, forgetting meetings..."

Theme 2: Prioritisation and Planning Skills

"...problems with changing deadlines, hard to prioritise, time management."

"Lots of competing priorities can be difficult because they're challenging to schedule."

"...challenges with estimating how long a task will take so I can often run out of time or need to work late to complete things."

Theme 3: Task Transition Effort

"I have difficulty switching between tasks."

"I struggle when there are many tasks to jump between."

"I do however struggle to get back on task when I'm interrupted."

Theme 4: Distractions

"I also find it hard to focus on my work if I am distracted by someone's overly strong or unpleasant perfume."

"...getting distracted every 10 seconds... distracted by noise/conversations."

"Can't focus."

Theme 5: Understanding Expectations

"I used to struggle a lot with thinking if I'm not 100% productive every second of the day, I was lazy and letting everyone down."

"But is not being productive really a problem? I mean whose problem is it?"

"I don't understand what level of productivity my employer expects of me... no employer seems willing to give any employees explicit permission to slow down/take more breaks. I live in doubt as to whether I'll someday be caught and punished for not working at the fast and efficient pace that's unsustainable for me."

Q8: Do you use any specific tools or techniques to overcome these problems, difficulties or issues with regards to productivity, organisation and executive function around getting work done? This could be using a particular platform for organisation or following a productivity model like pomodoro.

Theme 1: General Lists and Notes

“When my manager is generally telling me thing to do or ideas, I write them down immediately on a post-it. I then transfer this to my running list when I am at my computer.”

“Take a lot of notes and have to have admin type procedures written out to refer to or I forget.”

“Lists, plan a timetable.”

Theme 2: Pomodoro

“I do use pomodoro.”

“I use pomodoro for doing long-form writing.”

“I have tried pomodoro to remind myself to take a 'stretch-my-legs-break'.”

Theme 3: Calendars and Notifications

“I have also asked my team to start using Word's assign feature when they need me to do something so it registers that I need to take action.”

“alarms... people to remind me about things, other physical reminders in view...”

“I use the Tasks function in Google Calendar because I get dopamine from checking things off and you can schedule tasks WAYYY in advance.”

Theme 4: Creating 'work mode'

“...getting moved to a 'better' seat, away from too much footfall and one with fewer desks nearby.”

“...wearing headphones in the office, or working from home, helps me to mitigate the problems of becoming distracted.”

“...easier to error check spreadsheets or do other fiddly work when I know there won't be any interruptions.”

Theme 5: Trying Many Different Tools

“Google Keep; Tabwave; sticky notes”

“Trello boards, Padlets...”

“Habitica, using a random number generator to choose my task.”

Q9: Beyond tools and techniques, is there anything else you do personally to overcome these problems, difficulties or issues with regards to productivity, organisation and executive function around getting work done?

Theme 1: Extra Effort, Extra Hours

“Trying to manage my adhd as best as I can.”

“I have had to take work home to finish it over the weekend.”

“Sometimes I have to try and force myself to do work.”

Theme 2: Self Care, Self Kindness

“Try and be kind to myself, try and be more physically active, fresh air/sun exposure.”

“sleep; exercise; supplements”

“Accepting that working at 100% capacity all the time is actually detrimental to my work output because I burn out really quickly that way.”

Theme 3: Therapy and Medication

“Therapy to help with the guilt around feeling like things have to be perfect or done well.”

“medication! it helps!”

“have an Occupational therapist.”

Theme 4: Managing WFH Environment

“Working from home, doing everything digitally so it's available across multiple devices.”

“I try to focus on what I can control.”

“Wearing headphones in the office, or working from home, helps me to mitigate the problems of becoming distracted.”

Theme 5: Habits and Breaks

“Take a break from it, do something creative which helps get flow state (basically anything that doesn't involve that part of my brain, and instead involves hands on things - crafting, cooking, gardening).”

“If I've hit a brick wall then I look at the plants in the office - I guess it's like meditation or mindfulness. I focus on all the details of it then return to my work usually more focussed.”

“Working a slightly off schedule (9-6) from the norm (7:30-4:30) in my department guarantees me uninterrupted time every day.”

Q10: What mitigations does your workplace put in place to help with any problems, difficulties or issues with regards to productivity, organisation and executive function around getting work done?

Theme 1: Nothing

"I haven't requested mitigations. (I'm not sure how to do so without revealing my neurodivergent status at work.)"

"None, all self-motivated/produced."

Theme 2: Extra Guidance

"My library has a procedures file with an outline of almost every main task within the library. This can be very helpful when experiencing brain fog and I need to look quickly at how to do something."

"We have one on one meetings every other week to gauge progress, etc. Also get due dates for things."

Theme 3: Social Accommodations

"They allow me to take microbreaks as they know it helps my productivity. Like they aren't concerned if I'm staring out of a window for too long as they know I'm not slacking off but rather refocussing my brain"

"We do have periodic discussions about how we each organize ourselves."

Q11: What would the hypothetical "perfect" work amount, type or structure, or tool or technique, be like for you?

Theme 1: More Hours in the Day

"Clearly delineated tasks and deadlines, and the time allowed to do them justice!"

"Able to pace things with proper time allocated to tasks."

"...so much of my day is going to pointless meetings, talking to people, and other tasks that take me away from my actual job."

Theme 2: Instructions

"A widely available and communicated procedure documented for all tasks."

"I could do with more help with breaking down tasks and projects."

"A list of things to do with clear instructions and deadlines."

Theme 3: Routine and Predictability

"Something predictable, constant and manageable."

"A pattern of working from home and being on campus that never changes, and a pattern of having meetings in the morning followed by just deep desk work in the afternoon, and that never changes."

"minimising unexpected verbal requests that are harder to process."

Theme 4: Understanding

"A really caring, non-judgmental employer that was prepared to truly be flexible and understanding."

"A lot of my colleagues are neurospicy or have chronic illnesses, so it's a supportive environment overall."

"Non-hierarchical structure everyone has a real stake in that's run for the wider community."

Theme 5: Working from Home

"...do hybrid or work from home."

"For me personally, it would be a few days per week where I could WFH."

"...so I'm not stuck with bad lighting or other things that are tough to handle when I'm triggered."

Q12: Is there anything else you'd like to add about workload management?

Theme 1: Struggle

"It's very tough."

"It's real hard! I do feel REALLY lucky to have a good and supportive workplace, but that doesn't make it not difficult."

"It is a struggle and I am awaiting an ADHD diagnosis still."

Theme 2: Fear of Disclosure

"Disclosing my diagnosis at work might help but currently feels risky."

"...they don't know about my conditions."

"I've got a bit of 'cover' and I don't have to directly ask for these things."

Theme 3: Help

"I'm trying to get over the idea that it's rude to ask for help. I think that's hard for me because I never know if I'm being unintentionally rude, so I just assume imposing my workload on someone else, regardless of how willing they are to help, is incredibly rude, so I end up saying yes to everything and never asking for any help and completely drowning in work and struggling to keep my head above water."

"Just expecting me to "do the thing" without any guidelines or expectations of what my managers wanted from me was absolutely horrible and I don't recommend it."

"Project work is great, but doing a day job on top, and having line management responsibilities to contend with is too draining."

Theme 4: Concept of Work

"Sometimes also it is hard to explain exactly what you are doing to others so they might think it straightforward when really it is involving a lot of work."

"Meetings should count more as work, but for some reason don't."

"I don't think I can thrive in the current capitalist system of full-time work being required for survival. Even apart from workload, it's extremely stressful to me to have to continually prove my worth to my employer, on pain of homelessness. I could probably get much more work done (as a result of being less stressed & neurotic) if I were able to do it on my own terms (not relying on the approval of people and organizations with money for my survival)."

Supporting Resources

This is a summary of the most salient supporting resources that have sections relevant to this area.

1. [Neuro-Empowerment of Executive Functions in the Workplace: The Reason Why](#)

The Triadic Model of Executive Functions

2. [Children and Adults with Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder – summary of two models](#)

Barkley breaks executive functions down into four areas:

- Nonverbal working memory
- Internalization of Speech (verbal working memory)
- Self-regulation of affect/motivation/arousal
- Reconstitution (planning and generativity)

Brown breaks executive functions down into six different “clusters.”

- Organizing, prioritizing and activating for tasks
- Focusing, sustaining and shifting attention to task
- Regulating alertness, sustaining effort and processing speed
- Managing frustration and modulating emotions
- Utilizing working memory and accessing recall
- Monitoring and self-regulating action

3. [Agcas Disability Task Group - Reasonable Adjustments for Neurodiversity](#)

Challenge: Concentration and focus, Easily distracted, Procrastination, Fatigue

Examples of reasonable adjustments:

- Take short breaks throughout the day. Negotiate taking 10-15 minute breaks regularly away from your desk. This may mean working slightly longer core hours to accommodate this e.g. 8.30-5.30 rather than 9-5 would give you four 15 min breaks to take during the day when you needed them.
- Focus on one job at a time rather than multi-tasking when you may be distracted often
- Set a regular timer on phone or PC to bring you back to focus should you tend to go off track – can be visual or auditory. This needs to be intrusive enough for you to notice it.
- Use a “do not disturb” sign/function on your telephone and email, when specific tasks require intense concentration.
- Ask your employer to encourage co-workers not to disturb you unless absolutely necessary.
- Ask your employer if you can work somewhere that is quiet and away from distractions, for example away from doors, busy phones, loud machinery.
- Understanding any sensory issues, e.g. open plan offices have lots of noise and lights, which may be minimised by the use of desk partitions, telephones that light up when ringing, noise-cancelling headphones, desk low-lights etc.
- Ask about the possibility of working from home occasionally or coming in early or staying late, to reduce distraction, stress and fatigue.
- Relaxation techniques can help with concentration.

Challenge: Organisation and planning

Examples of reasonable adjustments:

- Ask for a workspace that is quiet and free from distractions such as doors, phones and loud machinery.
- Ask if it is possible to work from home occasionally.
- Ask for a workspace that is well lit, neat and tidy.
- Ask for a wall planner that visually highlights appointments, deadlines and tasks.
- Ask for reminders of important deadlines and regular reviews of priorities and projects.
- Ask for timetables, mnemonics and mind maps if these help with prioritising work and meeting deadlines.
- Colour code items in your workspace.
- Ask for a personal digital organiser.
- Use computer features such as calendars, alerts and alarms.
- Create a daily “To Do” list.
- Ask for work to be broken up into manageable chunks.
- Build planning time into each day.
- Allow extra time for tasks and projects, for unforeseen circumstances.
- Ask for templates for detailed work, such as reports.

Useful apps for helping keep you focussed.

These are just suggestions there will be others that work just as well and may suit your needs better.

- **Anti-Social** Set the app for your chosen time frame and it will block distracting social media websites. Currently only for Mac users.
- **SelfControl** This will block access to the websites that distract you the most for a set period that you determine. Until the timer expires, you will be unable to access those sites—even if you restart your computer or delete the application.
- **Write or Die** Set your time period, word goal, and preferred “punishment” should you stop typing. Once the setup is complete, you’ll need to type fairly continuously; otherwise, there will be consequences which you also choose. **Gentle Mode:** A certain amount of time after you stop writing, a box will pop up, gently reminding you to continue writing. **Normal Mode:** If you persistently avoid writing, you will be played a most unpleasant sound. The sound will stop if and only if you continue to write. **Kamikaze Mode:** You will need to keep writing or your work will start to overwrite itself.
- **StayFocusd** This is a free Chrome extension that will help you to stay more focused on your writing by restricting the amount of time you spend on distracting websites. You set a certain amount of time for social media for a day, after you have used your allotted time you will be blocked for the rest of the day.
- **Freedom** – app to block internet, messages and social media leaving you free to focus on your work

4. AskJan.org: Accommodation Solutions for Individuals with Executive Functioning Deficits

Time Management: Individuals may experience difficulty managing time, which can affect their ability to mark time as it passes incrementally by minutes and hours. It can also affect their ability to gauge the proper amount of time to set aside for certain tasks. As a result, it may be difficult to prepare for, or remember, work activities that occur later in the week, month, or year.

- Divide large assignments into several small tasks or chunks
- Set a timer to sound an alarm after assigning ample time to complete a task
- Provide a checklist of assignments
- Plan and structure times of transition and shifts in activities
- Supply an electronic or handheld organizer and train on how to use it effectively
- Use a wall calendar to emphasize due dates
- Develop a color-coded system (each color represents a task, or event, or level of importance)
- Allow co-worker or supervisor to add entries on the calendar or to double-check entries added by the employee

Memory: Individuals may experience memory deficits, which can affect their ability to complete tasks, remember job duties, or recall daily actions or activities.

- Provide written instructions and checklists
- Allow use of a recorder
- Allow additional training time for new tasks
- Offer training refreshers

- Provide minutes of meetings and trainings
- Use flow-chart to indicate steps in a task
- Provide verbal or pictorial cues
- Use a color-coding scheme to prioritize tasks
- Use notebooks, planners, or sticky notes to record information
- Use sticky notes as reminders of important dates or tasks
- Provide labels or bulletin board cues to assist in location of items

Concentration: Individuals may experience decreased concentration, which can be attributed to auditory distractions and/or visual distractions. Distractions such as office traffic and employee chatter, opening and closing of elevator doors, and common office noises can be problematic.

- To reduce auditory distractions:
 - Provide a noise canceling headset
 - Hang sound absorption panels
 - Provide a white noise machine
 - Relocate employee's office space away from audible distractions
 - Redesign employee's office space to minimize audible distractions
- To reduce visual distractions:
 - Install space enclosures (cubicle walls)
 - Reduce clutter in the employee's work environment
 - Redesign employee's office space to minimize visual distractions
 - Relocate employee's office space away from visual distractions
- Breaks for mental fatigue, including short walks, getting up for a drink of water, and rotating through varied tasks
- Job restructuring so the most difficult tasks are performed at the time of day the employee has the most mental energy or stamina

Organization and Prioritization: Individuals may have difficulty getting or staying organized, or have difficulty prioritizing tasks at work.

- Develop color-coded system for files, projects, or activities
- Use a color-coding scheme to prioritize tasks
- Use weekly chart to identify daily work activities
- Use a job coach to teach/reinforce organization skills
- Assign a mentor to help employee
- Allow supervisor to assign prioritization of tasks
- Use electronic organizers, mobile devices, and e-mail reminders
- Assign new project only when previous project is complete, when possible
- Provide a "cheat sheet" of high-priority activities, projects, people, etc.
- Organize work space to reduce clutter
- Provide separate work areas with complete sets of supplies for differing tasks
- Schedule a weekly time to clean/organize work space
- Take time at the end of each day to organize and set up for the next day

Multi-tasking: Individuals may experience difficulty performing many tasks at one time. This difficulty could occur regardless of the similarity of tasks or the frequency of performing the tasks.

- Separate tasks so that each can be completed one at a time

- Create a flow-chart of tasks that must be performed at the same time, carefully labeling or color-coding each task in sequential or preferential order
- Provide individualized/specialized training to help the employee learn techniques for multi-tasking (e.g., typing on a computer while talking on the phone)
- Identify tasks that must be performed simultaneously and tasks that can be performed individually
- Provide specific feedback to help the employee target areas of improvement
- Remove or reduce distractions from work area
- Supply ergonomic equipment to facilitate multi-tasking
- Clearly represent performance standards such as completion time or accuracy rates

Paperwork: Individuals may experience difficulty completing paperwork efficiently and effectively. This may be due in part to workplace distractions and difficulty with time management, disorganization, or prioritization.

- Automate paperwork by creating electronic files when possible
- Use speech recognition software to enter text or data into electronic files
- Save time filling out paper forms by completing information in advance, using pre-filled forms, or adhering pre-printed stickers
- Use checklists in place of writing text
- Provide templates of letters or e-mails
- Color-code forms for easy identification
- Re-design commonly used forms
- Use large font
- Double space or triple space
- Provide adequate space for hand-written response

Social Skills: Individuals may have limitations in exhibiting appropriate social skills. This might manifest itself as interrupting others when working or talking, demonstrating poor listening skills, and inability to communicate effectively.

- Provide a job coach to help understand different social cues
- Identify areas of improvement for employee in a fair and consistent manner
- Encourage employees to minimize personal conversation, or move personal conversation away from work areas
- Provide sensitivity training (disability awareness) to all employees
- Encourage all employees to model appropriate social skills
- Adjust the supervisory method to better fit the employee's needs
- Adjust method of communication to best suit the employee's needs
- Allow the employee to work from home

Attendance: Individuals may have difficulty getting to work promptly because of the varied activities, processes, and interruptions they may experience while preparing to leave their home and/or during their commute.

- Allow flexible work environment:
- Flexible scheduling
- Modified break schedule
- Work from home/Flexi-place

Getting to Work on Time: Employers can have time and attendance standards for all employees. Because getting to work on time is the responsibility of the employee, the following ideas are for employees who are having trouble getting to work on time because of executive function deficits:

- Have a routine of putting and keeping things in their place (keys, phone, glasses)
- Prepare for the next day's work the night before
- Create a checklist for yourself and others
- Place sticky notes on the door, dashboard, or wherever you will see them
- Turn off distractions – including cell phones
- Set a timer or a programmable watch to pace yourself

5. [AskJan.org: Solutions for Executive Functioning Deficits](http://AskJan.org)

Very comprehensive list of suggestions of accommodations with USA based products and services that provide them in the following areas:

- Apps for Concentration
- Apps for Memory
- Calendars and Planners
- Checklists
- Colour Coded Systems
- Cubicle Doors, Shields and Shades
- Environmental Sound Machines / Tinnitus Maskers / White Noise Machines
- Extra Time
- Flexible Schedule
- Form Generating Software
- Full Spectrum or Natural Lighting Products
- Job Coaches
- Job Restructuring
- Marginal Functions
- Modified Break Schedule
- Noise Cancelling Earbuds
- Noise Cancelling Headsets
- On-site Mentoring
- Recorded Directives, Messages, Materials
- Reminders
- Sound Absorption and Sound Proof Panels
- Speech Recognition Software
- Sun Boxes and Lights
- Sun Simulating Desk Lamps
- Timers and Watches
- Written Instructions

6. Awareness Leaflets

The Neurodiversity Hub

[How to Get the Best Out of Your Autistic Employee](#)

[Working Memory Strategies](#)

[Executive Functioning Strategies](#)

Partnership for Employment Outcomes for Autistic People in Society

[Simple Adjustments You Can Make](#)

7. Crowdsourced Tools and Techniques

- Routinary
- To-Do List
- Habit Tracker
- Remember The Milk: To-Do List
- MindNode
- Forest
- Joon
- Teiimo
- Trello
- Asana
- Monday.com
- Toggl
- RescueTime
- Focusmate
- Google Keep
- Paper planners
- Bullet journals
- Grammarly
- Texthelp
- Kapwing
- Pomodoro
- Drucker Time Management
- Eat the Frog
- Kanban
- This video: [Toxic Productivity Advice for ADHD](#)

Conclusion and Recommendations

While not all problems uncovered in this survey ultimately have a solution, particularly with Q7 where the top theme was that this was just a feature of their neurodiversity and always will be, most of the common answers could either be supported with either an accommodation, or increased understanding.

Many were repeated across responses, for example:

Set A

- Extra hours
- Prioritisation
- Planning
- Buddies
- Advance warning
- Interruptions

And these could all be mitigated with simple accommodations, like those listed in the supporting resources above, and following through on those. Suggested accommodations from those resources that would remove most of the difficulty of Set A responses include:

- Someone else managing calendars or prioritisation of tasks
- 'Body Doubling' and accountability partners
- Giving enough notice of work
- Allowing blocking off of focus time
- Providing a quieter work space

Another set of common responses included those that would be mitigated with increased understanding and allowing things that might seem different, for example:

Set B

- Task Transition Time
- Routine and Predictability
- Understanding Expectations
- Managing Emotions and Reactions
- Saying No

These could all be mitigated not by changing anything about the workplace, but by kindness and understanding, or by adequately separating these aspects from performance and capability. Suggested accommodations from those resources that would remove most of the difficulty of Set B responses include:

- Allowing more frequent breaks
- Allowing working from home
- Spending more time answering clarification questions
- Allowing more time to respond
- Accepting a negative response

Finally, there was a third set of responses, that could be described as aspects that would help anybody on any team, whether neurodivergent or neurotypical. These included:

Set C

- Autonomy
- Clear instructions
- Deadlines
- Flexibility
- More hours in the day

And could be supported by, for example:

- Adequate staffing
- Adequate planning and 'thinking through'
- Allowing decisions to be made about own work practices
- Having core hours of 10-4 for meetings
- Allowing out of hours emails but not expecting responses
- Communicating across whole teams on personal work preference

Neurodivergent staff are already within current teams, and as this report highlights, are not revealing this. Many respondents said that they did not know what to ask for and did not want to disclose difficulty, and this report has the potential to inform and empower newly instigated conversations in this area, and to enable neurodivergent staff to make changes that will increase their performance.

While not a full research study, the above report is comprehensive, and perhaps offers a better understanding of practical solutions with lived experience and summarised evidence to enable leaders and managers to support neurodivergent talent in teams, particularly library teams. Implementing appropriate suggestions from this report and increasing understanding through absorbing the information within it will hopefully lead to the unlocking of skills and talent within existing teams, increasing efficiency and impact.

To engage further with Neurospicy Libraries:

Website

<https://neurospicylibraries.wordpress.com/>

Forum

<https://neurospicylibraries.flarum.cloud/>